

University of Pécs, CoARA Action Plan 2025-2029

Introduction

The University of Pécs (Hungary) is committed to implementing the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, with the initial focus being on delivering the four core commitments in the order identified by the working group. This will be supported by five cross-cutting institutional actions: review, resources, awareness, monitoring, and exchange. This action plan covers the period 2026–2029. A *Center* will be established for managing CoARA actions, research reform, and promoting open science, reporting to the University's Rector and responsible for coordinating implementation. The Center, chaired by a senior academic, should comprise representation from senior researchers, early-career researchers, and research support services (Library, HR).

Commitment 1: Recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research

Our goals include (1) expanding the definition of 'research contribution' to encompass areas beyond traditional journal articles. This could include data curation, software creation and maintenance, open infrastructure, peer review services, policy engagement, innovation, the integration of teaching and research, and mentorship and leadership roles, for example; (2) establishing a system to recognize and reward diverse career paths, including non-linear and team-based contributions; (3) ensuring that hiring, promotion, research funding and internal awards reflect this broader understanding of contributions.

Commitment 2: Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer-review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators

The goals here are: (1) to shift institutional evaluation practices (e.g. hiring, promotion, internal grants and internal benchmarking) towards qualitative review as the main assessment mode, with quantitative metrics playing a strictly supporting role; (2) to establish guidelines and training for peer-review-based assessment committees at all levels; (3) to define a 'responsible metrics' policy that clarifies which indicators may be used and how and when they should be used, ensuring that they support qualitative evaluation rather than replacing it.

Commitment 3: Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index

Our goals here are: (1) to discourage inappropriate institutional reliance on JIFs, h-indices, or other similar metrics for hiring, promotion, internal funding, or internal awards; (2) to ensure that research outputs are evaluated on their individual merits rather than the perceived prestige of the publication venue; (3) to establish transparent guidance on which quantitative indicators may be used, and to limit their use to responsible and contextualized applications as supplementary evidence.

Commitment 4: Avoid the use of rankings of research organizations in research assessment

The goals here are: (1) to eliminate reliance on third-party rankings in internal institutional evaluations, hiring, promotions, internal funding or research strategy decision-making; (2) to ensure that strategic goals, resource allocation and internal ambitions are based on mission-

driven metrics and qualitative reflection, rather than ranking positioning; (3) to document and clearly communicate how the university engages with external rankings, and to ensure that ranking results are not used for internal individual assessments.

Further Institutional Commitments

To deliver on the core CoARA commitments, we propose five further commitments, in order of priority as identified by the University.

Commitment 6: Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes

The center commissions a review of current research assessment practices across the institution. This review should map where metric reliance, narrow output definitions, or ranking-based assessment might distort behavior. Based on the review, the center develops a revised institutional assessment framework that: uses a broad taxonomy of research contributions; places qualitative peer review at the center of evaluation and includes contextualized quantitative indicators only where appropriate and supplementary. Introduce “contribution portfolios” or narrative research portfolios in hiring, promotion and internal grant procedures, replacing or enriching publication-list-plus-metrics models. Pilot revised tools and processes (e.g. new portfolio templates, peer review rubrics, contribution-based evaluation formats) in selected faculties/departments, evaluate feedback and refine.

Commitment 5: Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organizational changes

A dedicated budget line should be established for research assessment reform, covering staff time (e.g. a part-time reform coordinator, a secretariat for the center and administrative support), training workshops, the engagement of consultants or external experts (if needed) and the development of digital tools (e.g. interfaces for portfolio submission, training modules for reviewers and dashboards for monitoring reform progress). Protected time should be allocated for center members to participate in reform activities (training, workshops, piloting and consultation).

As part of our four-year CoARA Action Plan, the university intends to set up a center, either at faculty level or across the whole university. This center will serve as a hub for training, support and innovation in open science practices, transparency and trustworthy research. Taking inspiration from similar initiatives and existing Hungarian communities, the center will strengthen research quality, credibility, and societal trust. By the end of the four-year plan, the university will assess the feasibility of setting up the center, complete with a clear governance structure, funding model and integration into existing research support services. The center will become a focal point for embedding open science and research reform practices across disciplines, thereby enhancing both internal cultural change and the external visibility of our commitment to trustworthy research.

Commitment 7: Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training

Develop and publish a university research assessment reform charter that summarizes our CoARA commitments, explains the practical implications of research assessment reform, and sets out the new expectations for researchers, peer reviewers, and committees. Launch a communications campaign comprising seminars, intranet posts, newsletters and faculty meetings to inform the university community about the CoARA agreement, the rationale for

reform and the proposed changes. Create and deliver a training program for: (a) peer reviewers and committee chairs; (b) applicants and researchers preparing portfolios/narrative contributions; and (c) research support staff on how to assist with reform processes (e.g. helping researchers construct contribution narratives and showing responsible metrics). Publish clear guidelines and templates for contribution portfolios, narrative CVs, peer review rubrics, responsible metrics and prohibited metrics/rankings. Ensure these are easily accessible on a university website or intranet and are updated regularly.

Commitment 9: Communicate progress made on adherence to the principles and implementation of the Commitments

Set up a monitoring and reporting framework with defined KPIs and qualitative feedback loops to track progress. Examples include the proportion of evaluation committees using the new portfolio formats, the number of reviews or promotion cases referencing prohibited metrics, the number of training sessions delivered and the number of participants involved, feedback satisfaction from applicants and reviewers, and anecdotal qualitative feedback on perceived fairness and transparency. Publish a CoARA reform report including narrative and quantitative indicators of progress, challenges encountered, lessons learned and planned next steps. Present the report to the university's leadership and governance bodies (e.g., the university senate and Doctoral or Habilitation Committee), and publish an abridged version on the university's website or in its institutional repository. Periodically review the action plan based on monitoring data, stakeholder feedback and evolving best practices, updating the plan as needed.

Commitment 8: Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition

The center contributes to the CoARA community by uploading its action plan and subsequent reports or updates to the CoARA Zenodo community and by participating in CoARA webinars and workshops. We establish institutional collaborations and peer-learning partnerships with other CoARA signatories in the region to share best practice, lessons learned, and tools. The center should encourage researchers and research support staff to attend CoARA-related workshops and national or European communities of practice on research assessment reform. We host or co-host at least one peer-learning event on research assessment reform at the university that is also open to external partners.

Actions & Indicators

Timeline	Action	Responsible	Indicators
2026 Q1– Q3	Map and review current evaluation practices, assessment processes, identify gaps	Center, HR	Report; procedures reviewed
2026 Q4– 2027 Q2	Draft guidelines (peer review central, metrics supportive only, JIF/h-index use) and Responsible Metrics Policy	Center, University Library and Knowledge Centre, Rector	Draft taxonomy & portfolio format endorsed

Timeline	Action	Responsible	Indicators
2027 Q3– 2028 Q1	Consultation with faculties, institutes, Doctoral/Habilitation Committee	Center	Nr. of consultations; Nr. of faculties/institutes/committees engaged
2028 Q1– Q3	Draft taxonomy of contributions and portfolio format, pilot portfolios in 2–3 faculties	Center, Institute Chairs, Doctoral/Habilitation Committee	Pilot portfolio; participant feedback
2028 Q4– 2029 Q4	Training on responsible metrics and peer-review	Center, University Library and Knowledge Centre	Nr. of training sessions; Nr. of people trained
2026 Q3– continuous	Formal adoption and communication	Rector, Communications Office	Policy published & communicated
2028 Q1– continuous	Monitor and refine	Center, Rector	Nr. of assessments citing qualitative review as primary

Risks and mitigation

Risk	Mitigation
Resistance from faculty or committees accustomed to traditional metrics	Engage with stakeholders early and often. Include respected senior researchers in the Center. Run pilot programs with local champions. Provide training and communication that emphasizes fairness, transparency, and improved recognition of diverse contributions.
Reform is implemented unevenly across disciplines or faculties	Conduct discipline-specific consultations and pilot the use of templates in a variety of faculties. Encourage local adaptation and monitor the uptake and feedback from faculty members and disciplines.
Poor uptake of training or new tools	Incentivize participation (e.g. by certifying committee chairs who complete training and recognizing reform lead roles), ensure training is accessible and practical, collect feedback and adapt accordingly, and embed guidance in official policy documents to make training part of committee responsibilities.
Continued covert use of metrics or rankings	Maintain monitoring processes such as annual reports and feedback loops. Champion transparency by publicly communicating new policies. Include reform champions in internal review committees or evaluation panels. Revise policies and tools if non-compliance is detected.